

THE THREAT OF EXTREMISM TO NATIONAL SECURITY AND STABILITY

Kurbanov Djamshid Djurayevich

Head of the Department of UNI Academic Lyceum,

Independent Researcher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: This article presents the current experience in combating extremism, as well as a retrospective and comparative analysis of the situation in the countries of the region in combating these threats.

Keywords: globalization, extremism, civil servants, society, terrorism

In the current globalization and the ongoing transformation of international and regional conflicts, the issue of effective fight against extremism and terrorism remains one of the urgent topics on the agenda. At the same time, extremist and international terrorist organizations continue to spread violence and radical views in society by inciting youth to violence, to lose their national identity, cultural-educational and family values under the guise of religious beliefs. All this creates conditions for citizens to join the ranks of extremist and terrorist organizations. In this regard, determining more effective measures aimed at preventing and ending extremism and terrorism, as well as eliminating the sources and channels of their financing, as well as combining efforts at the national and international levels in this regard, are important directions of state policy.

According to the manifestation of religious extremism, it is divided into regional, regional and international forms. Such views have very ancient roots, religious extremism has never known borders, does not recognize nation, territory, and has developed within all religions. No matter where and under which religious banner religious extremists operate, their main ideological goal is to establish a religious state, and this goal is achieved through conflicts, armed conflicts, that is, bloodshed.

At a time when the struggle for the mind and soul of humanity has acquired a new qualitative character, it is important to emphasize the commonality of faith (for example, pan-Islamism), the emphasis on ethnic unity (for example, pan-Slavism), and the dependence caused by living in a single socio-economic and political space. It should be noted that there are attempts to ideologically divide the world space by ensuring the dominance of single ideologies on the basis of alienation (for example, Pan-Sovietism).

Today, it can be seen that the interests of extremist groups are manifested in the following:

- political goals aimed at changing the state administration, socio-economic system and internal policy;
- economic interests aimed at derailing the economy by acquiring strategically important properties, enterprises and structures of organizations and certain individuals;
- creating ethnic-national conflicts directed at representatives of certain nationalities and national groups against other nationalities and national groups living in the same territory;
- aimed at creating disorder among civil servants and goals aimed at eliminating the structures of society that use force;
- religious terrorism aimed at seizing power by some extremist groups under religious slogans;
- criminal terrorism aimed at discrediting the government, creating an atmosphere of fear and mistrust in the society through theft, robbery and invasion by invading groups consisting of various criminal elements.

The strategic goals of religious extremist terrorist organizations in Uzbekistan are the creation of a theocratic state based on Sharia, and for this purpose, the following is envisaged:

- “Islamization” of the population on a large scale;
- destabilization of social and political situation;

➤ intensifying inter-religious and inter-ethnic relations;

➤ establishing strong relations with religious-extremist organizations operating abroad, using their opportunities in training the group's fighters and providing material and technical support for their activities.

The main methods of activity of religious extremist organizations are as follows:

- distribution of leaflets, literature, video and audio tapes in a religious extremist spirit, including the ideas of “jihad”;
- inculcating radical Islamic concepts taught in secret “cells”;
- strong condemnation of the socio-political situation in Uzbekistan;
- discredit official religious structures;
- creation of secret groups and special training of its members;
- trying to include their supporters in state structures;
- strengthening cells consisting of women;
- effective use of terrorist means [1].

In conclusion, it is known that such religious extremist and terrorist organizations carry out their evil actions on the basis of plans and specific goals by creating a comprehensive, reliable cooperation with all terrorist structures and actions, mutual interest, both material and financial unity.

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